

THE ISSUE OF ASSESSING THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF GENERAL
SECONDARY SCHOOL SERVICES

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Abstract. *The article contains a number of issues devoted to studying the issue of assessing the synergistic effectiveness of the services of general secondary schools. In addition, this work analyzes the methodologies and indicators used to evaluate the services of general secondary schools. Specific indicators and systematic approaches are proposed to measure synergistic effectiveness.*

Keywords. *Modernization, resource, efficiency, inclusive, state, society.*

The school education system plays an important role not only in providing knowledge, but also in ensuring the personal and social development of students. Based on the principle of synergy, all elements of the educational process - teachers, students, parents, school administration, and other community advocates - must work together and effectively combine resources and capabilities to achieve a common goal. The goal is to determine how effectively school services work as a whole and assess its synergistic results, that is, what maximum results can be achieved from the interaction of all participants.

The issue of assessing the synergistic effectiveness of preschool and school education services is of great importance as the basis for the effective, progressive and sustainable development of every society and state. We can take a closer look at the reforms being implemented in the education sector, the renewal of advanced pedagogical approaches, the mechanisms for improving the quality of education, and the creation of educational systems tailored to the needs of students. The issue of infrastructure, the introduction of digital technologies, the updating of curricula, and the improvement of the skills of teaching staff are important for the modernization of the education system.

The implementation of actions to improve and develop the education system is closely and inextricably linked not only to the Republic, but also to us, to all active points of society. It is clear to all of us that the Head of State's words, such as "The development of school education must become a nationwide movement...", are sufficient confirmation of the above reasoning.

Also, implementing this movement into continuing education is one of the effective methods.

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The need to bring a new spirit to all parts of the education system has been repeated before, but the saddest thing is that it has only been said, written, spoken, and forgotten. Our current actions may allow us to correct the mistakes we made in the past. The current system of continuing education in Uzbekistan is internationally recognized and based on world experience. The preschool education system has been rebuilt, and reforms in general education and higher education have significantly changed the attitude of our citizens towards science. I believe that we have no right to stop at this very moment or repeat old mistakes.

Access to higher education has increased to such an extent that a large portion of the population has earned degrees in a fairly wide range of fields. Now only those with knowledge and intellectual potential are selected. As I noted above, our existing continuing education system meets international standards, but we have many pain points and problems within the system. We believe that for quality education, we should focus on three main aspects: using and learning the materials we receive as independently as possible; organizing groups in the classroom for discussions and practical exercises; and improving your knowledge, skills, and competencies with all the information you gain from your class or group discussions. In addition, the quality of education can be simplified into two stages: the first is providing quality education, and the second is receiving quality education. Currently, we are confusing these concepts or giving them one-sided importance.

The first condition has a driving characteristic. That is, the knowledge and skills of the teacher speak for themselves here. It should be a "guide" for learners with its historical name.

The second stage is directly related to learners. That is, the class of those who process the knowledge and information they have received. The more a learner can expand, supplement, and, most importantly, refine their knowledge, the better their education will be. The development of the education system is extremely important for the future of society, as education directly affects the economic, social, and cultural development of a country.

There are several key issues in the development of the education system today, some of which include the following. Quality of education and inclusion: The primary goal of the education system is to provide quality education to students of all ages. Inclusive education involves creating opportunities for all groups, that is, eliminating differences based on social or economic status.

This requires equal provision of educational opportunities not only in multi-ethnic and multicultural societies, but also in rural and urban areas.

Integrating digital education and technology: A modern education system must be integrated with digital technologies.

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It is necessary to make the learning process of students more effective through the use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) in education, distance learning, interactive platforms, and online resources.

Teacher qualifications and professional development: Teachers are the most important part of the education system. It is necessary to ensure their professional development, train qualified and motivated teachers, master new pedagogical technologies, and apply innovative approaches to education.

Graph 1

The rate of change in the total share of educational services in Kashkadarya region
in 2017-2023 (%)

Educational services in Kashkadarya region totaled 3464.3 billion soums, an increase of 2.6% in 2014, 3.1% in 2015, 3.8% in 2016, 5% in 2017, 6.7% in 2018, and 8.5% in 2019. These indicators have changed significantly between 2020 and 2023. This can also be seen in the graph.

The change in the basic method is 283.6 billion soums in 2020, 473 billion soums in 2021, 542.1 billion soums in 2022, and a significant change of 89.7% in 2023.

Renewal and modernization of educational programs: Adapting educational programs to modern requirements is one of the important issues. This means providing students with not only traditional knowledge, but also the skills needed to think creatively, solve problems, use technology, and function effectively in society.

Infrastructure and logistics: Creating the necessary infrastructure is essential for the education system to function effectively.

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This includes the material and technical support of schools, equipping classrooms with modern technical equipment, and updating and expanding educational resources and materials.

Aligning education with economic and social development: the education system should serve not only to provide scientific knowledge, but also to meet the needs of society. It is important to develop educational programs that meet the country's economic development and labor market demands, and to focus on vocational education.

Equality and gender issues in education: It is necessary to ensure gender equality in education and create equal opportunities for all groups. This includes protecting the rights of women and girls to education and further involving them in the education system.

Financial resources and investments in education: It is necessary to attract the necessary financial resources to develop the education system and develop a policy aimed at encouraging public and private sector investment in education. This is necessary to improve the quality of education, build new facilities, support teachers, and allocate resources effectively.

The issues listed above set the main directions for effectively developing the education system, creating equal opportunities for all members of society, and ensuring that students are competitive with global requirements. Issues related to the development of the education system directly affect the future stability and progress of society. It is necessary to improve the quality of education, introduce new pedagogical approaches and innovative technologies, improve the skills of teaching staff, and adapt the educational process to modern requirements.

This requires transforming the education system into an inclusive and digital one, strengthening school infrastructure, updating educational programs, and providing students with the skills they need to succeed not only academically, but also in life. Also, the development of the education system should be supported not only by the state, but also by the private sector and all segments of society.

Focusing on improving finances, infrastructure, educational resources, and pedagogical skills is essential for developing the education system. Only through such a comprehensive approach can the education system serve not only the social and economic development of society, but also the success of students in a global and modern world.

At the same time, the development of the education system should be aimed primarily at creating equal opportunities for all citizens, ensuring social justice, and providing future generations with comprehensive, modern, and solid knowledge.

Conclusion

The results help to develop recommendations aimed at improving the quality of education by establishing effective cooperation and integration between all participants in the education system. This, in turn, increases the effectiveness of schools in educating students as useful, well-rounded individuals for society. Evaluating synergistic effectiveness helps integrate all parts of the education system. Applying the principle of synergy in evaluating school services helps improve the quality of education and help students maximize their potential. Therefore, the joint and effective work of all participants in the educational process serves the progressive development of society.

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